

Data Management Plan v1.0 for SAMBa

1. Purpose and scope

The SAMBa project will generate diverse biodiversity monitoring data from automated sensors deployed in controlled environments (e.g., greenhouses), established field experiments, and real-world sites. These data streams will be complemented by eDNA workflows, expert annotations, species-trait databases, and statistical and modelling analyses. The data-management strategy must therefore support both high-volume sensor outputs and curated ecological knowledge products.

The purpose of this data management plan is to define how data will be:

1. collected in the field, greenhouse, laboratory, and computational workflows;
2. transmitted from monitoring devices and partners to LIB infrastructure;
3. stored, backed up, curated, and quality-controlled during the project;
4. processed into reproducible biodiversity observations and indicators;
5. linked to metadata, taxonomies, traits, uncertainty estimates, and provenance information;
6. integrated with, but not dependent on, the LIB Open Knowledge Space;
7. archived, published, and licensed according to FAIR and CLEAR principles.

The DMP will be treated as a living document and updated at least once per project year, and additionally after major methodological changes, new data types, or changes in infrastructure.

2. Relevant policies and principles

Research data management in SAMBa will follow:

- DFG guidelines on the handling of research data and good scientific practice;
- DFG guidelines for biodiversity research data;
- FAIR principles: findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable;
- CLEAR principles for semantic interoperability and human explorability;
- LIB research data management policies;
- Leibniz Association principles on open access and good scientific practice;

- relevant biodiversity data standards, including Darwin Core, ABCD, Dublin Core, MixS where applicable for molecular data, and suitable multimedia metadata standards for image and acoustic assets.

All datasets will be documented with persistent identifiers where possible, versioned metadata, clear provenance information, and explicit links between raw data, processed data, analysis scripts, model versions, and resulting indicators.

3. Data infrastructure overview

SAMBa will use a tiered data infrastructure that separates operational data management from semantic knowledge integration. This ensures that the project can be operated independently of the LIB Open Knowledge Space, which is currently under development, while still allowing for integration at a later date.

The planned architecture is:

Data acquisition layer

Data originate from:

- BUGSI (SAMBa basis) devices deployed in greenhouses, field experiments (PaNDiv, BugNet, PhenoRob), and real-world sites (FINKA, Eifel National Park);
- eDNA laboratory workflows and sequencing;
- expert annotations and taxonomic validations;
- trait and taxonomy reference systems;
- external environmental and remote-sensing datasets.

BUGSI contributes additional operational data streams:

- telemetry (CPU temperature, battery state, WLAN status, buffer size, uptime);
- device-status logs from the BUGSI daemon and local webserver;
- configuration snapshots (local + SaaS-synced);
- OTA update metadata;
- structured detection images (crops + full frames).

Each observation is linked to device IDs, deployment IDs, and sampling-event IDs.

Ingestion layer

Data enters SAMBa through automated and manual workflows that include:

- checksum validation and file-integrity checks;
- device authentication via API keys (BUGSI);
- structured metadata templates;
- upload logs and provenance records;

- automated parsing of sensor metadata (timestamps, GPS, environmental logs);
- telemetry ingestion via BUGSI API endpoints;
- configuration synchronization and OTA update polling.

This ensures traceability and reproducibility from the moment data are acquired.

Primary storage layer

All raw data are stored in an immutable archive on LIB-managed infrastructure, including:

- original sensor files (images, DVS, audio);
- environmental logs and device-status logs;
- raw sequence files and laboratory metadata;
- telemetry tables (PostgreSQL);
- device configuration versions (JSON);
- OTA package manifests;
- onboarding logs and API key issuance records.

Raw data are never overwritten; corrections occur only in derived datasets.

Curation and processing layer

Operational data are transformed into structured, quality-controlled products using:

- project databases and asset-management systems (Diversity Workbench, fyflr, PostgreSQL, CKAN);
- workflow pipelines for image, acoustic, and eDNA processing (YOLOv9, Detectron2, NVIDIA DeepStream, QIIME2, vsearch);
- BUGSI backend services (FastAPI, PostgreSQL 16, React dashboard);
- device-client daemon for preprocessing, buffering, and upload scheduling;
- annotation tools for expert review (e.g., BTO Acoustic Pipeline, Label Studio);
- automated QC reports and uncertainty assessments.

This layer produces curated datasets suitable for modelling and indicator development.

Analysis and indicator layer

Reproducible analytical workflows generate:

- taxonomic observations and detection events;
- trait annotations derived from the species-trait database;
- confidence scores and uncertainty estimates;
- multimodal biodiversity indicators linking sensor outputs, traits, treatments, and environmental context.

- device-level quality flags derived from telemetry (e.g., overheating, low battery, WLAN downtime).

This layer forms the scientific backbone for evaluating biodiversity responses to land-use and management practices.

Integration and publication layer

Processed and curated data products are exported to:

- the LIB Open Knowledge Space (semantic integration and knowledge-graph layer);
- GBIF, GFBio, and other biodiversity infrastructures;
- NCBI/ENA/SRA for sequence data;
- GitHub/GitLab for code, workflows, and model documentation;
- the LIB Digital Asset Management System (fylr) for long-term archiving and discovery.

This layer ensures FAIR/CLEAR compliance and enables reuse by researchers, practitioners, and policy makers.

4. Expected research data

4.1 Sensor data

SAMBa will generate high-volume sensor data from automated biodiversity monitoring devices, especially BUGSI and associated modular sensor units.

- Expected sensor data include:
 - dynamic vision sensor data;
 - RGB/IR images and image sequences;
 - acoustic recordings;
 - environmental sensor data (temperature, humidity, wind, light);
 - device-status logs (battery, uptime, error states, firmware version);
 - BUGSI telemetry (CPU temp, WLAN state, buffer size, power mode);
 - detection images (crops + full frames);
 - configuration snapshots and OTA metadata.

Raw sensor files will be stored in non-proprietary or widely supported formats wherever possible. Images will be stored as TIFF, JPEG, PNG, or RAW-derived archival formats depending on scientific need. Acoustic recordings will be stored as WAV or FLAC where feasible. Environmental logs and device-status logs will be stored as CSV or JSON, with metadata in XML, JSON-LD, or CSV.

Each sensor unit will receive a persistent device ID. Each field installation will receive a deployment ID. Each observation period will receive a sampling-event ID. These identifiers will link sensor outputs to field metadata, environmental conditions, annotations, model outputs, and final indicators.

4.2 eDNA and molecular data

The project will generate eDNA and metabarcoding data from field and laboratory workflows.

Expected molecular data include:

- sample metadata;
- extraction metadata;
- PCR and library preparation metadata;
- sequencing run metadata;
- raw sequence files;
- quality-filtered sequence files;
- ASV/OTU tables;
- taxonomic assignment tables;
- negative and positive control results;
- bioinformatic workflow reports.

Molecular data will follow established eDNA/metabarcoding metadata standards where applicable, for instance metabarcoding data will be stored in the ASV Registry (<https://asv.bolger.de/>). Raw sequence data will be deposited in suitable repositories such as NCBI SRA or ENA. Processed tables and workflow outputs will be stored in project repositories and linked to publications and public datasets.

Physical samples and DNA extracts will be archived in the LIB Biobank where appropriate, with links between biobank identifiers, sampling-event IDs, and molecular datasets.

4.3 Annotation and training data

Because SAMBa includes self-learning and expert-in-the-loop components, annotation data are a central research output rather than a temporary processing artifact.

Annotation data include:

- image labels;
- acoustic labels;
- organism detections;
- taxonomic identifications;

- trait annotations;
- uncertainty ratings;
- expert reviewer identity or role, where appropriate;
- annotation date;
- annotation tool version;
- model-assisted pre-labels;
- final accepted labels.

Annotations will be versioned. Changes to labels will be traceable, especially when expert corrections are used to retrain models. Training, validation, and test sets will be stored as separate, versioned datasets to avoid leakage between model training and evaluation.

4.4 Trait, taxonomy, and reference data

SAMBa will generate and use trait-based reference data for multi-taxon biodiversity indicators.

These data include:

- taxonomic names and identifiers;
- synonym mappings;
- functional traits;
- trophic roles;
- habitat associations;
- activity patterns;
- co-observations
- body size and morphology-related traits;
- links to external taxonomic and trait repositories;
- provenance of trait assertions;
- confidence or evidence level for trait records.

Trait and taxonomy data will be curated in structured tables and, where possible, represented in interoperable formats that can later be exported to the LIB Open Knowledge Space. The operational trait database will remain usable independently as CSV/TSV exports, relational database tables, and versioned releases.

4.5 Field, experimental, and management data

SAMBa will generate heterogeneous biodiversity monitoring data from automated sensors deployed in greenhouse experiments, established field experiments (PaNDiv, BugNet, PhenoRob), and real-world deployment sites such as FINKA and Eifel National Park. These data streams include:

- plot-level metadata;
- spatial and temporal information;
- treatment metadata (e.g., pesticide applications, plant-diversity levels, mowing regimes, fertilization, intercropping, or restoration measures, where available);
- landscape context and habitat descriptors derived from remote-sensing products;
- maintenance logs and records of deviations from protocol;
- stakeholder feedback on usability and operational feasibility.

Field and experimental data will be stored in structured tables with a dedicated Naming convention, using controlled vocabularies wherever possible. Spatial data will be recorded in decimal degrees with explicit coordinate-reference-system information. Sensitive species or site information may be generalized or access-restricted when required. All occurrence-based data will be imported into the LIB's central collection-management system, Diversity Workbench, which serves as the central hub linking SAMBa's monitoring outputs with curated taxonomic and ecological knowledge.

5. Data collection and acquisition

All data collection will be linked to a sampling-event record before data are uploaded or processed. This record will contain the minimum metadata needed to interpret the data later.

Minimum metadata for each sampling event will include:

- project name;
- site name;
- plot ID;
- sampling-event ID;
- device ID or sample ID;
- date and time in ISO 8601 format;
- time zone;
- geographic coordinates;
- habitat or management context;
- responsible person;
- sensor configuration or laboratory protocol version;
- calibration status;
- weather or environmental context where available;
- data-use restrictions if any.

For automated sensors, metadata will be captured partly on-device and partly through deployment forms. Field teams and practitioners will use standardized digital forms. Offline-capable forms will be used for remote locations.

For laboratory data, electronic lab notebooks or standardized digital templates will be used to document sample handling, extraction, amplification, sequencing, and quality-control steps.

6. Data transmission

SAMBa will use two complementary data transmission modes.

6.1 Automated transmission

Where mobile network, Wi-Fi, or local network access is available, sensor devices will upload data automatically or semi-automatically to LIB infrastructure.

The upload procedure will include:

- encrypted transfer;
- device authentication;
- resumable upload for unstable field connections;
- checksum generation before and after transfer;
- automatic upload logs;
- confirmation of successful transfer;
- flagging of incomplete or corrupted files.

Low-volume data such as environmental logs, device-status logs, and detection summaries may be transmitted more frequently than high-volume image, DVS, or acoustic data. Additionally we implement buffered uploads when offline. Once device are installed, test images will be transmitted directly to allow users to adjust and calibrate the system based on immediate visual feedback (WLAN timer logic in battery mode).

6.2 Manual transmission

Where network coverage is insufficient, data will be stored locally on encrypted or access-controlled storage media and transferred manually during field maintenance.

Manual transfer will include:

- registration of storage media;
- checksum validation;
- upload to the raw-data landing zone, e.g. the LAUP Portal from the LEPMON project;

- confirmation that data were successfully copied;
- documentation of transfer date and responsible person.

This dual strategy ensures that SAMBa remains operational in both well-connected and remote field conditions.

7. Data storage during the project

SAMBa will use a three-zone storage model.

7.1 Raw-data landing zone

The landing zone is the first storage location for incoming files. It is used for upload validation, virus scanning where applicable, checksum verification, and metadata completeness checks.

Files in this zone are temporary and will be moved either to the raw archive or to a quarantine folder if validation fails. The submission workflow follows the OAIS Standard (ISO 14721) that is implemented in the GFBio Datacenter at LIB.

7.2 Immutable raw-data archive

All validated raw data will be stored in an immutable or write-protected raw-data archive. Raw files will not be overwritten. Corrections will be made in derived datasets, never by modifying original files.

The raw archive will contain:

- original sensor files;
- original sequence files;
- original environmental logs;
- original field forms;
- original annotation exports;
- original laboratory records where applicable.

Each raw-data package will include metadata and checksums.

7.3 Curated project database and asset storage

Processed, curated, and annotated data will be stored in dedicated project databases and asset systems.

Depending on data type, SAMBa will use:

- LIB-managed storage for large sensor assets, like the LAUP data infrastructure developed in the LEPMON project;

- The Digital Asset Management System *fyfr* for multimedia assets where appropriate;
- Diversity Workbench modules for collection, specimen, trait, or biodiversity metadata where appropriate;
- relational databases such as PostgreSQL for structured project data;
- GitLab or GitHub for code, workflow definitions, documentation, and versioned releases;
- institutional backup systems for active project data.

The operational database will be designed so that SAMBa can produce indicators and publications without requiring the Open Knowledge Space to be complete or operational. The Open Knowledge Space will receive curated exports and semantic mappings from this primary project infrastructure.

8. Relationship to the LIB Open Knowledge Space

The LIB Open Knowledge Space will be used as a semantic integration and knowledge-discovery layer, not as the sole operational data-management system.

The operational SAMBa data infrastructure will remain independently functional and will include:

- raw-data archive;
- curated project database;
- multimedia asset storage;
- molecular data repositories;
- annotation database;
- model registry;
- workflow repositories;
- indicator datasets.

Curated and validated data will be exported to the Open Knowledge Space through defined interfaces and semantic mappings. These exports may include taxon observations, trait annotations, provenance records, confidence scores, links to raw-data packages, and indicator outputs.

This separation reduces implementation risk. SAMBa can produce validated datasets and indicators even if Open Knowledge Space integration is delayed, while still ensuring that the final system contributes to LIB's long-term semantic biodiversity infrastructure.

9. Archiving, publication, and licensing

SAMBa will follow an open-data-by-default approach, except where legal, ethical, conservation, or partner restrictions require limited access.

Planned publication routes include:

- GBIF for occurrence data where suitable;
- GFBio or NFDI4Biodiversity-supported repositories for biodiversity datasets;
- Zenodo for publication-linked datasets and software releases;
- NCBI SRA or ENA for sequence data;
- MorphDBase or easyDB for selected multimedia assets;
- GitHub or GitLab for code, workflows, documentation, and model cards;
- LIB Biobank for biological samples and DNA extracts.

Datasets linked to publications will be deposited before or at the time of article publication and cited with persistent identifiers. Data will generally be licensed under CC BY 4.0, unless restrictions require a different license. Software will be released under an appropriate open-source license, such as MIT, Apache 2.0, or GPL, depending on dependencies and institutional guidance.

All data required to reproduce published results will be preserved for at least ten years according to good scientific practice and institutional policies.

10. Responsibilities

The group leader will have overall responsibility for research data management.

Operational responsibilities will be distributed as follows:

- Group leader: overall DMP implementation, infrastructure decisions, compliance with LIB and funder policies, approval of public releases.
- PhD researcher for sensor and pipeline development: sensor data ingestion, processing workflows, model versioning, annotation workflows.
- PhD researcher for indicators and field validation: field metadata, management metadata, indicator datasets, statistical analysis outputs.
- Technical assistant: laboratory and field documentation, sample tracking, data upload support.
- LIB Biodiversity Data Center / RDM support: data schemas, repository selection, archiving workflows, metadata standards, DOI preparation.
- Collaborating LIB centres: taxonomy, trait, AI, database, and knowledge-system support.
- External collaborators and practitioners: site-specific field metadata, deployment support, and feedback according to agreed templates.

A short annual data audit will check whether datasets, metadata, code, and documentation are complete and whether storage needs have changed.

11. Estimated data volume and storage needs

Because SAMBa will generate high-volume sensor data, final storage needs will be refined after the first greenhouse and field pilot deployments. A provisional estimate is:

- image, DVS, and camera data: approximately 30–60 TB;
- acoustic data: approximately 5–20 TB, depending on sampling frequency and compression;
- environmental and device logs: below 0.5 TB;
- eDNA raw and processed data: approximately 0.2 TB;
- annotation and training datasets: approximately 1–5 TB;
- model outputs and intermediate processing files: approximately 5–20 TB;
- final curated indicator datasets and statistical outputs: below 1 TB.

The project plans for an initial storage allocation of at least 50TB, including raw data, processed data, backups, and intermediate files. This estimate should be reviewed after Year 1.